

Effect of Learning Camp Program in English on Language Proficiency of Grade II Learners

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Abstract. The study explored the impact of a learning camp program in English on the language proficiency of grade II learners at Binugao Central Elementary School, Davao City. Addressing the gap in reading proficiency between English language learners (ELLs) and native speakers, the study aimed to find effective instructional strategies for young learners, particularly those with disabilities. Using a quasi-experimental non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design, the research involved 60 grade II pupils split into control and experimental groups. The intervention included blended learning sessions combining online meetings and printed modules over three weeks. Pre-tests and post-tests assessed language proficiency, and data analysis used mean scores and Eta squared for effect size determination. Results showed both groups started at the 'Beginning' level, but post-test scores significantly improved for the experimental group, with a mean increase of 6.2 points to 'Approaching Proficiency.' Statistical analysis confirmed the program's effectiveness with a t-value of -5.37 and a p-value of .0344. The Eta squared value of 0.421 indicated substantial effect size. The study concludes that the learning camp program significantly enhanced the language proficiency of grade II learners. It recommends adopting such programs to improve language proficiency and suggests further research to validate their effectiveness in different educational settings.

KEY WORDS

1. Learning Camp 2. Language Proficiency 3. Grade II Learners

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1. Introduction

To achieve academic and personal success, students must learn to read with understanding from an early age and refine and strengthen these skills over time. Successful English readers develop functional knowledge of the English alphabetic writing system and apply it as they begin to read words in print moving from less to more complex challenges as they encounter new vocabulary and progressive more difficult text. For people, whose native language is English, learning to read is complicated by the relationship between reading and speaking skills. Lack of familiarity with the sounds in English words may hinder English language learners' understanding of the relationship between sounds and letters in print. Moreover, learning to read academic text may present even greater challenges because English language learners have fewer meaningful opportunities to practice academic language than conversational language. (Snow, Burns, Griffin, 2021). National and state assessment scores highlight a

significant gap in reading proficiency between English language learners (ELLs) and native English speakers, a gap that widens as students advance through their education (National Center for Educational Statistics, 2020). This issue becomes even more concerning when considering the minimal progress of ELLs who have disabilities. Like the general student population, some English language learners also have special needs, including language, academic, behavioral, or physical challenges that impede their literacy acquisition and ability to grasp increasingly complex content. Often, it is said that English learners face “double the work” as they strive to understand academic material while simultaneously mastering the English language. Consequently, ELLs with learning disabilities (such as dyslexia or dysgraphia) or speech and language disorders (such as auditory processing issues or expressive/receptive language disorders) encounter even greater obstacles (Chard, Vaughn, Tyler, 2020). Given that students facing these challenges need more intensive instructional efforts, educators can benefit from guidance and support in applying effective, research-based teaching methods for English literacy and academic content to English language learners with disabilities. This publication addresses various issues and offers recommendations for meeting the needs of English learners with limited language proficiency, learning disabilities, or both. We start by highlighting the current federal policy context relevant to this discussion on reading instruction and interventions for ELLs (Gersten, Brengelman, Jimenez, 2021). It is essential to discuss the processes for identifying and classifying English language learners and to address related assessment issues and concerns based on the diagnosed problem. Following this, we will explore the challenges in identifying ELLs with disabilities and the difficulties of the learners in accurately assessing their academic achievements and language proficiency. We will then review recent research on instruction and

interventions for ELLs, offering recommendations within the framework of the Response to Intervention model. Finally, we will consider professional development issues. In the Davao City Division, specifically in the Binugao District, early grade students struggle significantly with language proficiency, particularly in decoding and comprehension. Students have difficulty decoding words and understanding what they read. A summertime learning program was implemented with the hope of improving their language proficiency. As a grade two teacher, the researcher aims to explore and evaluate the initial impact of this summer reading program on the language proficiency of grade two students (Chard, Ketterlin-Geller, Baker, Doabler, 2022).

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—The related literature supports the existence of the research problem and serves as a roadmap for the study.

1.1.1. Linguistic Performance—A multiple baseline design was employed to assess an intervention program’s impact on the oral reading rate and comprehension of five struggling primary school English-language learners. This program included vocabulary instruction, error correction, and fluency building. Significant improvements in oral reading rates and comprehension were observed when using the same passage until achieving a target fluency (Fitzgerald, 2021; Grossen Carnine, 2021).

Teachers could base second-language reading instruction on research with native English speakers, though adjustments might be needed. However, current research primarily focuses on enhancing basic reading skills and strategic behaviors for students with learning disabilities (LD). Effective teaching methods include vocabulary instruction, error correction, and repeated readings, although their impact on reading comprehension remains uncertain (Graham Johnson, 2021; Mastropieri Scuggs, 2020).

Vocabulary instruction is essential for read-

ing comprehension. Effective methods involve providing clear definitions, fostering higher-order thinking skills, and ensuring repeated exposure to new words (Linan-Thompson et al., 2023). There is a need for further research to investigate vocabulary instruction's effects on poor readers and those with learning problems, particularly regarding maintenance and generalization (Jitendra et al., 2021).

1.1.2. Error Correction—Teacher feedback on student errors during oral reading tasks is crucial. Immediate correction of errors has been advocated, although some suggest prioritizing the construction of meaning in feedback (Grossen Carnine, 2021; Hoffman, 2021). Effective strategies in correcting oral reading support struggling readers, emphasizing fluency, defined as the ability to read text quickly and accurately (Tyler, 2022).

1.1.3. Repeated Readings—Repeated readings significantly improve reading fluency and comprehension. The National Reading Panel reported a moderate positive impact on reading achievement from guided repeated oral reading (O'Shea et al., 2021). Conducting three or four repetitions of the same passage leads to substantial fluency and comprehension improvements (Scruggs, 2021).

1.1.4. Fluency and Comprehension—A reciprocal relationship exists between fluency and comprehension. Slow reading hinders active text engagement due to working memory consumption (Chard et al., 2022). Accelerated reading rates have been shown to improve both decoding accuracy and comprehension (Scruggs, 2021). Teachers should help struggling readers set specific, challenging, yet achievable goals, with self-recording as an effective progress monitoring tool (Vaughn, 2020).

In summary, a structured reading program employing direct instruction and mastery learning should focus on vocabulary instruction, error correction, and repeated readings to enhance

reading fluency and comprehension. Future research should refine the criteria for repeated reading and explore the optimal number of trials for maximum fluency gains (Chard et al., 2022).

The present study investigated the effects of an intensive intervention program on the oral reading rate and reading comprehension of elementary-level English-language learners who were struggling readers.

1.2. Synthesis—The above-stated review of significant literatures discussed the prevalence of the problem under study in different context. They also discussed methodologies on how the current issue is solved. There are findings and recommendations presented to resolve the problem. These literatures backed up the occurrence of the problem and different localities present solutions. They also serve as roadmap to guide the researcher in the conduct of the study.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—This study is rooted in Stahl's theory (2020), emphasizing the critical importance of communicative competence, particularly in the context of second language acquisition for our learners. Stahl proposes leveraging learners' primary language as a foundational resource in their path to mastering a second language, noting that students with robust literacy skills in their native language often acquire English more quickly. According to Vaughn et al. (2020), it is recognized that many concepts are first grasped in the learner's primary language and can subsequently be transferred and elaborated upon in the second language. The diagram that follows illustrated the flow of this experimental research. The action initiated is the learning camp in English and it hopefully affects the language proficiency of the grade two learners. It is hoped that using this approach, the academic performance of the students will be increased.

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study

1.4. *Statement of the Problem*—This study sought to determine the learning camp in English, on the language proficiency of the grade two learners. Eventually, it also sought to determine the magnitude of effect of the action initiated by the researcher on the language proficiency of the research subjects. Moreover, it sought answer to the following sub-problems:

- (1) What is the pre- test scores of the experimental and controlled group?
- (2) What is the post-test scores of the experimental and controlled group?
- (3) Is there a significant difference on the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental and controlled group?
- (4) What is the magnitude of difference between scores of pre-tests and posttest of experimental and controlled group?
- (5) What is the magnitude of effect of the learning camp in English on the language proficiency of the grade two learners?

1.5. *Null Hypothesis*—This null hypothesis of this study was tested at 0.05 level of significance. H01. There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the controlled and experimental groups. H02. Learning camp in English effect on the language proficiency skills of the grade two learners.

1.6. *Significance of the Study*—The following are considered beneficiaries of this action research. School Administrators- it allows the school administrators to solve their own problems and evaluate the effectiveness of their own professional practice. Teachers- a teacher with a wide range of extraordinary benefits but it is a fun experiment for kids as well and they

will certainly appreciate the entire experience to begin with. Future Researchers- a study about the effect of the learning camp on the academic proficiency of learners in any discipline is hereby recommended as another study of future researchers.

1.7. *Definition of Terms*—To make this study comprehensive, the following terms are operationally and conceptually defined. Learning Camp refers to the activities of the learners in English that are categorized as intervention. Consolidation and enhancement. This is designed to develop the learners' skills and competence based on the mandated learning competencies set by the department of education.

Language Proficiency refers to the ability of the learners in English subject articulated into grades. According to Wikipedia (2020), language proficiency is in fact complex phenomena. The nature and characteristics of a particular instance of linguistic performance and its product(s) are, in reality, determined by a combination of factors.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher had access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

- 01 Pretest of the experimental group
- 02 Posttest of the experimental group
- 03 Pretest of the controlled group
- 04 Posttest of the controlled group
- Non-random assignment of subjects
- X Treatment applied in the experimental group

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School, Binugao District, Division of Davao City. The subjects of this study were the 60 grade two pupils – 30 were from section A which was the controlled group and 30 were from section B which was the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B had identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	Section	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	30
2	Section B	30
Total		60

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It was a blended learning where the teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher had to meet the learners online for a follow up session of what had been printed in the module. The pre- and post-performance test consist of a 25 –item test was

eventually determined the reading skills of the research subjects. The pretest was administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest was very helpful to assess language proficiency of the grade two learners. On the other hand, posttest was administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the language proficiency of the grade two learners, the following continuum was used based on DepEd rating system.

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City and the school principal of Binugao Central Elementary School. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school prin-

icipal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission had been granted that this study be conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School and after the research questionnaire had been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher had administered pretest to both controlled and experimental class and even-

tually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher had administered posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher made analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean was used to describe the language proficiency of the grade two learners. Eta square was used to measure the magnitude of effect of learning camp program on the language proficiency of the grade two learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They were discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequences: pre-test scores of the learners, post-test scores of the learners, and the significant relationship between the pre-test and post-test scores.

3.1. *Pre-Test Score of Learners*—Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade two learners. The controlled group got the mean of 13.1 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 15.3 or Beginning.

Table 1: Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Control Group	30	13.1	52.4	Beginning
Experimental Group	30	15.3	61.2	Beginning

Looking at the table, it is evident that during the pre-test, the experimental group had a higher average rating compared to the controlled group, despite both being at the beginning level. This finding aligns with the insights of Linan-Thompson et al. (2023), who emphasize that effective vocabulary instruction involves providing clear definitions and contextual information for new words. Their approach encourages active learning and ensures multiple exposures to meaningful information related to words and their contexts. A thorough examination of existing literature reveals a gap in the use of vocabulary instruction, error correction strategies, and repeated readings for ESL students with LD. Vocabulary knowledge is crucial for reading comprehension, particularly as

students with LD often struggle with vocabulary deficits (Carlisle, 2020). Ongoing research explores various methods of vocabulary instruction tailored to the needs of students with LD (Vaughn et al., 2020).

3.2. *Post-Test Score of Learners*—Table 2 displays the post-test scores of second-grade learners. The controlled group achieved a mean score of 20.1, indicating a developing level, while the experimental group achieved a mean score of 21.5, indicating an approaching level. It is evident from the table that during the post-test, the experimental group outperformed the controlled group, showing a mean score increase of 6.2 from their initial mean score of 15.3 to 21.5. This demonstrates significantly better performance by the experimental group compared

to the controlled group. This finding resonates with Tyler's (2022) assertion that there is a need to explore effective practices in oral reading correction to support struggling readers and those with reading difficulties. Tyler defines fluency as the speed and accuracy with which students read text aloud, emphasizing its importance in reading development.

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Control Group	30	20.1	80.4	Developing Proficiency
Experimental Group	30	21.5	86.0	Approaching Proficiency

The use of repetition in a basic reading skills training program showed that three or four repeated readings of the same passage led to positive gains in fluency and comprehension of the passage; the effects diminished as the number of readings exceeded four trials (Simmons, 2021).

3.3. *Difference between the Pre-test and Post-test Scores*—Table 3 illustrates the statistical analysis conducted to assess the difference between pretest and post-test scores among the

respondents. The analysis yielded a t-value of -5.37 with a corresponding p-value of .0344, indicating statistical significance at the .05 level. This suggests a notable disparity between the pretest and post-test scores of grade two learners. These findings suggest that the implementation of the learning camp program in English has significantly enhanced language proficiency among grade two learners, as evidenced by their performance scores.

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	37	-5.37	.0344	Significant

This finding aligns with Gersten's (2020) assertion that communicative competence holds relevance for those engaged in second language acquisition. Effective reading instruction programs should prioritize specific teaching strategies supported by robust experimental research, aimed at enhancing the fluency necessary for comprehension. Research indicates a reciprocal relationship between fluency and comprehension, where improvements in one typically enhance the other (Vaughn et al., 2020). How-

ever, ongoing discussions surround the precise nature of this relationship. Many struggling readers and individuals with learning disabilities often lack automatic or incidental reading skills. The theory of automatic information processing posits that slow reading consumes working memory, limiting active engagement with the text (Chard et al., 2022).

3.4. *Magnitude of Difference*—Table 4 demonstrates the impact of the social interaction approach on the historical appreciation skills of

grade two learners, showing a substantial Eta2 value of 0.421. This indicates a significant effect size, suggesting that educators should seek effective teaching strategies in English that engage learners' interests. In today's interconnected world, English proficiency is increasingly vital, offering enhanced educational, career, and social prospects. To address this need,

various educational institutions and entities have introduced learning camp programs aimed at enhancing English language skills. These programs, characterized by their immersive nature, provide a fertile ground for language development, with English teachers playing a pivotal role in their implementation and success.

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade 2 Pupils

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
60	-4.35	0.421	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Implementing a well-designed approach to teaching within a learning camp program aimed at improving English proficiency can lead to notable improvements in student outcomes. By integrating such strategies, educators can develop a robust and engaging learning environment that significantly boosts students' English language skills. While research literature offers limited empirical evidence on effective instructional methods for English-language learners, three

specific strategies—vocabulary instruction, error correction, and repeated readings—have been identified as beneficial for enhancing word recognition and reading fluency, critical components for effective comprehension. Despite the positive impact observed on oral reading skills, the extent of these strategies' influence on overall reading comprehension remains uncertain (Graham Johnson, 2021).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents a synthesis of the researcher's findings, conclusions, and recommendations following a thorough analysis and interpretation of the study's results. The primary objective of this research was to assess how a learning camp program in English impacts the language proficiency of grade two learners.

4.1. Results—Employing a quasi-experimental design known as a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design was deemed appropriate due to the intact nature of the learner groups. This approach was chosen to facilitate comparison between the controlled and experimental groups within the study's setting at Binugao Central Elementary School, Binugao District Division of Davao City. The study involved 60 grade two pupils, evenly split with 30 in Section A (control) and 30 in

Section B (experimental), both groups demonstrating homogeneous academic performance. The findings indicate that implementing the English learning camp program significantly enhanced the language proficiency of grade two learners, as evidenced by improved academic performance measured through post-test scores. The study also highlighted the substantial difference in outcomes between the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions were drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade two learners in both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group are at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching level.

4.3. *Recommendations*—Considering the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching grade two use a learning camp program in English on language proficiency as a strategic approach. English teachers can adopt to maximize the effectiveness of learning camp programs in enhancing students' language proficiency. A learning camp program focused on English language proficiency for grade two students can be highly beneficial. A camp setting can provide an immersive experience where students focus intensely on language skills. It allows for more individualized attention and tailored instruction to meet the specific needs of each

student, especially those who might be struggling. The school heads should promote the use of a learning camp program in English for the language proficiency of grade two learners. These intensive, immersive programs offer a unique environment for language acquisition, and English teachers play a pivotal role in their success. Combining immersive experiences, intensive practice, interactive learning methods, and continuous assessment to foster significant improvements in participants' language abilities. A school policy on promoting the use of a learning camp program in English for language proficiency can be issued. Besides, the said program can be highly beneficial for students. He can invite the teacher-researcher to demo-teach during the LAC session using social interaction as a strategy in teaching to ensure that the teachers running the camp are well-trained. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of a learning camp program in English on language proficiency as a strategy in teaching be conducted. Another dimension of teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

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